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Research Article

Optimum Combination of Crop Farm Activities: Application of a Linear Programming Model to a Rural Farmer in Zimbabwe

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ABSTRACT

Farm planning problems are much more complex. Farmers do not only produce different crops, but also have to choose among a variety of ways of producing them. Crop planning may involve choices about varieties, planting dates, fertilizer and pesticide treatments. Linear programming has proved a very flexible tool for modeling these kinds of complexities. In this paper, a linear programming model was developed to determine the optimal crop combination for a rural farmer. Crops considered were maize, soya beans and cotton. The model produced an optimal crop combination that gives higher income than that obtained from the farmer's plan. The income difference was 72.79 percent.

Keywords: Linear Programming, Maize, Rural Farmer, Optimum Crop Combination, Income.

INTRODUCTION

Farm planning problems are much more complex (Hazell and Norton, 1986). Farmers do not only produce different crops, but have to choose among a variety of ways of producing them (Hazell and Norton, 1986). Crop planning may involve choices about varieties, planting dates, fertilizer and pesticide treatments (Hazell and Norton, 1986). Linear programming (LP) has proved a very flexible tool for modeling these kinds of complexities (Hazell and Norton, 1986). Mohamad and Said (2011) proposed an LP crop mix model for a finite-time planning horizon. Their model incorporated the crop rotation requirements. Their model was solved for selected vegetable crops using LINDO. Their results indicated promising returns. If properly implemented, the results will enhance farm income Mohamad and Said (2011).

Igwe, Onyenweaku and Nwaru (2011), developed an LP model to determine the optimum enterprise combination using 2009/2010 farm data in Abia State in Nigeria. Their model incorporated constraints such as food consumption. The objective of the model was to maximize the gross margin of farmers involved in a combination of selected arable crops and fisheries. Out of the twelve production activities, made up of ten cropping activities and two fish enterprises, only two were recommended by the model for farmers to achieve a gross income of N342, 763.30. Igwe, Onyenweaku and Nwaru (2011) argue that, "This will help in enhancing food security among rural farmers in the study area in particular and the country in general." In a study by Majeke *et al* (2013), an LP model was developed to determine the optimal crop patterns and the optimal number of breeding sows. The results obtained by using LP were compared with those obtained from using existing plans by the farmer. The strategies obtained by using LP techniques yields more income than strategies from existing plans. In another study by Majeke (2013), an LP model was developed for a farmer in Marondera, Zimbabwe. The objective of the study was to maximize net income through optimal enterprise combination subject to resource constraints. The results showed that LP model suggestions are worthy putting into practice.

Igwe and Onyenweaku (2013) applied LP technique to farm data obtained from thirty arable crop farmers during 2010 farming season to maximize gross margin from various combination of arable crops and livestock enterprises. The results of their LP model were significantly different from the existing plan. The gross margin

obtained were 61.35 percent of the existing plan. Scarpari and Beauclair (2010) developed an optimized planning model for sugarcane farming using an LP tool. The results support the LP model developed as a very useful tool for

sugarcane management. Ibrahim and Omotesho (2011) determined an optimal enterprise combination for vegetable production under Fadama in north central Nigeria. Their LP model considered both economic and environmental goals simultaneously in a composite objective function. The optimal plan obtained achieved 88 percent of the goals considered. Abdelaziz *et al* (2010) used LP technique to analyze data. The results of the analysis showed that the models gave a cropping pattern different from the existing farmers' production plan. The results from LP models gave a profit while the farmers' plan resulted in a loss (Abdelaziz *et al*, 2010). Kaur *et al* (2010) successfully formulated an LP model to suggest the optimal cropping pattern for maximizing net returns and ensuring significant savings of ground water with the aim of sustaining groundwater use in Punjab. Linear programming models have successfully been formulated under different scenarios to model different kinds of complexities.

In this study, an LP model was formulated to determine the optimal crop combination for a rural farmer in Bindura, Zimbabwe. Crops considered were maize, soya beans and cotton.

Linear Programming Formulation

The rural farmer considered in this study has 6 hectares of land that is meant for crop production. Crops which were considered are maize, soya beans and cotton. The farmer's expected net returns for 2011/12 were \$610/ha from soya beans, \$170/ha from cotton and selling price of \$285 per ton for maize. The farmer's production plan was to allocate 4 hectares for maize, 1 hectare of soya beans and 1 hectare of cotton. Of interest is whether this crop combination yields maximum net returns. The farmer is also interested in satisfying the family maize consumption requirement of one ton. The farmer must decide on how many hectares that should be allocated to each

Table 1: Potential Enterprises and Resource Requirements

Resources	Quantity Available	Crops		
		Maize (ha)	Soya beans (ha)	Cotton (ha)
Crop land (ha)	6	1	1	1
Labor (days)	295	30	30	40

Table 2: Gross Margins

	Maize (ha)	Soya beans (ha)	Cotton (ha)
Gross Margin (\$)	879	610	170

Table 1 and Table 2 show potential enterprises and resource requirements, and gross margins respectively. The LP model is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max } z &= \sum_{j=1}^n c_j x_j \\ \text{subject to} \\ \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} x_j &\leq b_i, \\ x_j &\geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

Where,

z = the objective function (\$).

c_j = net returns per unit of j^{th} activity (\$).

x_j = level of the j^{th} activity.

a_{ij} = i^{th} resource required per unit of the j^{th} activity.

b_i = supply level of the i^{th} resource.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The LP model was solved using MS Excel. The optimum cropping combination obtained from the LP model and the farmer's existing plan are presented in Table 3. The model suggests no production of soya beans and cotton. The cropped acreage of maize increased by 50 percent compared to the farmer's plan.

Table 3: Comparison of Crop Combinations

Crops	Farmer's plan (ha)	LP solution (ha)	% of Farmer's plan
Maize	4	6	150
Soya beans	1	0	0
Cotton	1	0	0
Total	6	6	100

Production levels are presented in Table 4. Production of various crops at the farm behaved in the order of acreage variations discussed above.

Table 4: Comparison of Cropping Productions

Crops	Farmer's plan (\$)	LP solution (\$)	% of Farmer's plan
Maize	5,163	10,269	198.90
Soya beans	610	0	0
Cotton	170	0	0

The resource utilizations of both the LP model and the farmer's plan are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Comparison of Resource Utilizations

Resources	Farmer's plan		LP solution	
	Land (ha)	Labor (days)	Land (ha)	Labor (days)
Available	6	295	6	295
Usage	6	190	6	180
% Usage	100	65	100	61
Left over	0	105	0	115
% Left over	0	36	0	39

Results on income are presented in Table 6. The farmer's income would be increased by \$4,326. Income increased from \$5,943.00 to \$10,269.00 showing an improvement of 72.79 percent. The LP model increased income. The results show that the LP model suggestions maximize farmer's return whilst at the same time allowing him/her to meet his/her demand of food needs of maize.

Table 6: Comparison of Income Levels

Income		
Farmer's plan (\$)	Optimal solution (\$)	% of Farmer's plan
5,943.00	10,269.00	172.79

CONCLUSION

In this study, an LP model was developed to determine the optimal crop combination for a rural farmer. Crops considered were maize, soya beans and cotton. The model produced an optimal crop combination that gives higher income than that obtained from the farmer's plan. The income difference was 72.79 percent.

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